

**ORGANIZATIONAL MANAGEMENT AND PROGRAM PRACTICES OF
SELECTED NON-GOVERNMENT ORGANIZATIONS IN THE CITY
OF DASMARINÁS CAVITE: BASIS FOR POLICY
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Organizational Management and Program Practices of Selected Non-Government Organizations in the City of Dasmariñas Cavite: Basis for Policy Development Program

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Abstract

With this, the researcher aims to identify the organizational management practices of the non-government organizations and its program practices. This study utilized explanatory sequential approach of research. Moreover, the research focal point is to identify the organizational and policy practices of Non-Government Organizations. The respondents of the study were the presidents or general managers of the Non-Government Organizations in the City of Dasmariñas. Presidents or general managers were selected because in terms of organizational management, they oversee the day-to-day operations of the NGO, including managing staff, volunteers, and resources effectively. This involves making decisions about hiring, budgeting, and program implementation. By applying total population sampling, the researcher was able to get thirty-nine (39) respondents for its quantitative data. Moreover, the researcher utilized five (5) participants for the qualitative data. The qualitative data was gathered using interview. The findings show that respondents strongly agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of program impact. The finding suggests that the respondents held a positive perception of NGO program practices, strongly agreeing that these practices effectively result in meaningful program impacts. This high level of agreement, reflected indicates a consensus among respondents regarding the efficacy of NGO programs in achieving their intended goals and making a positive difference in the communities they serve. On the other hand, respondents agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of partnership. This concludes that respondents generally agreed with the level of program practices related to partnership exhibited by NGOs. However, indicates that while there is agreement, it may not be as strong or unanimous as in some other areas. This could imply that there may be room for improvement in how NGOs engage in partnerships, potentially through enhancing collaboration strategies, communication channels, or resource-sharing mechanisms.

Keywords: *organizational management practices, program practices, non-government organization*

Introduction

Non-government organizations have an immense role in the achievement of Millennium Development Goals, an initiative of United Nations (UN). According to UN, an NGO is a not-for-profit, voluntary citizens' group, which is organized on a local, national or international level to address issues in support of the public good. Task-oriented and made up of people with common interests, NGOs perform a variety of services and humanitarian functions, bring citizens' concerns to governments, monitor policy and programme implementation, and encourage participation of civil society stakeholders at the community level. They provide analysis and expertise, serve as early warning mechanisms, and help monitor and implement international agreements. Some are organized around specific issues, such as human rights, the environment or health. Moreover, according to the world bank, "NGOs as a private organization that pursue activities to relieve suffering, promote the interests of the poor, protect the environment, provide basic social service or undertake community development". In simple words, NGOs can be defined as, "Self-governing, private not for profit organizations that are geared improving the quality of life for disadvantaged people".

In the 1987 Philippine Constitution, the state is encouraged the formation of NGO under Article II and Article XIII, and also in the 1991 Local Government Code Section II C.

In the U.S., the formation of NGOs is fully supported by the government and government regulations. They're considered an important component of a civil society. There are about 1.5 million NGOs operating in the U.S., (Folger, 2024)

With a growing number of non-profit organizations focused on social services, the environment, education, and other unmet needs throughout the society, the non-profit organization sector is increasingly central to the health and well-being of the society (Panth, 2006). There are a number of problems faced by the non-government organizations like inefficient management, lack of resources, capacity building, performance measurement, resource mismanagement, and so forth.

The goal of NGOs can vary widely depending upon the specific focus, objective and mission of the organization. From improving human rights in a geographic area to providing education about environmental issues to supporting the arts, the goal or objective of an NGO can cover just about any topic related to improving a region, country or the state of the world in some way. Sharma (2023).

Hence, Aruna, et.al (2015) said that NGOs concerned with development face the management of a complex and diverse range of issues. NGOs face internal management issues, such as strategic planning, budgeting, staffing, and the governing structure of the organization, growth and change within the organization. NGOs also face the management of external relationships, relations with government, the private sector, other NGOs and with their target communities. All of these come to bear on the possibility of NGOs managing

development. The effectiveness of NGOs as actors in development and change depends on successful engagement with both internal and external management questions and also on the successful articulation between issues of internal and external management.

In the Philippines, nonprofit sector, including nongovernmental organizations, have enjoyed an enabling and facilitative state environment since the People Power Revolution of 1986. It currently faces a legitimacy challenge in terms of its ability to represent the people, to be accountable to them, and to show its autonomy and difference from the state. It also confronts the challenge of how it can deliver services more effectively as it expands and professionalizes. Raising resources through government, philanthropy, and income generation also continue to be major challenges. Cariño (1999)

The research locale of this study is at Dasmariñas Cavite. The city has a land area of 90.13 square kilometers or 34.80 square miles which constitutes 5.91% of Cavite's total area. Its population as determined by the 2020 Census was 703,141. (PhilAtlas, n.d), and has thirty-four (34) accredited non-government organizations.

With this, the researcher aims to identify the organizational management practices of the non-government organizations and its program practices. In studying this, a well-designed policy approaches will be proposed to enable NGOs to effectively advocate for social change, influence public policy, and advance their objectives. Hence, the importance of effective organizational management practices and policy approaches for NGOs lies in their ability to maximize their impact and contribute to positive social change.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the influence of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Math and Pupils' learning achievements in North City Central School Elementary School Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2023 - 2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the organizational management practices of the non-government organizations in terms of:
 - 1.1. planning;
 - 1.2. organizing;
 - 1.3. staffing;
2. What are the program practices of the non-government organizations in terms of:
 - 2.1. programs outcomes (effectiveness)
 - 2.2. non-financial efficiency;
 - 2.3. programs impact;
 - 2.4. partnership?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the organizational management and program practices of non-government organizations?
4. Based from the findings of the study, what policy development program can be proposed to enhance the operational practices of non-government organizations?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized explanatory sequential approach of research. The explanatory sequential approach, a mixed-methods research design, is a valuable tool for understanding complex phenomena. Yang (2019) highlight the importance of this approach in their respective studies on instrumental learning and multi-class decision-making. Nashed (2022) further extends this by presenting a unified framework for causal explanations in sequential decision-making systems. Ivankova (2006) provides practical guidance on implementing this approach, emphasizing the need to carefully consider the priority, sequence, and integration of quantitative and qualitative data. These studies collectively underscore the significance of the explanatory sequential approach in advancing our understanding of various phenomena.

Moreover, this approach involves two main phases: first, a quantitative phase to gather numerical data, followed by a qualitative phase to explain or interpret the quantitative results. In this initial phase, researchers collect quantitative data through surveys, experiments, or other structured methods. The focus is on gathering numerical data that can be analyzed using statistical techniques. The goal is to establish patterns, correlations, or relationships among variables related to the research question. After analyzing the quantitative data, researchers move to the qualitative phase to provide deeper insights and explanations for the quantitative findings. This phase often involves methods such as interviews, focus groups, or observations to gather rich, detailed data about participants' experiences, perspectives, and contexts. Qualitative data analysis techniques such as thematic analysis or grounded theory are then used to identify themes, patterns, or explanations that emerge from the qualitative data. Finally, researcher integrates the findings from both phases to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research question or phenomenon under investigation. This integration may involve comparing quantitative and qualitative results, triangulating findings to validate or enhance understanding, or using qualitative data to explain unexpected quantitative findings.

To align it with the purpose of this study, this was utilized by the researcher to leverage the strengths of the results in organizational

and policy practices of non government organizations, combining the breadth and generalizability of quantitative data with the depth and richness of qualitative data. By integrating these two types of data, researcher were able to develop more nuanced and comprehensive explanations of complex phenomena, leading to the proposal of the research output which is a policy development program to the non government organizations.

Participants

The research focal point is to identify the organizational and policy practices of non government organizations. The respondents of the study were the presidents or general managers of the non government organizations in the City of Dasmariñas. Presidents or general managers were selected because in terms of organizational management, they oversee the day-to-day operations of the NGO, including managing staff, volunteers, and resources effectively. This involves making decisions about hiring, budgeting, and program implementation.

By applying total population sampling, the researcher was able to get thirty-nine (39) respondents for its quantitative data. Moreover, the researcher utilized five (5) participants for the qualitative data. The qualitative data was gathered using interview.

Instrument

The study utilized self-made questionnaire. This research tool consists of a series of questions designed to gather information from individuals. The first part of the research questionnaire assessed the respondents' organizational management practices of non-government organizations in terms of planning, organizing, staffing, directing, and controlling. Moreover, the second part of the questionnaire was about the policy practices of non-government organizations in terms of accounting practices, planning and budgeting practices, and reporting practices.

Moreover, the interview guide questionnaire was based on the results of the quantitative data. The researcher's basis for the questions was the highest and the lowest in rank. Additionally, an interview-guided questionnaire ensures that the questions effectively capture the information or insights the researcher seeks and that the questionnaire reliably measures what it intends to measure.

Procedure

The researcher started the data gathering by asking permission from non-government organizations to conduct the research. After the approval, the first step was to explain the ethical considerations, objectives, process, and proposed output of the study.

For the quantitative phase, the researcher diligently disseminated printed questionnaires to the intended respondents. The answering process, which took approximately 10 to 15 minutes, was conducted with care. The researcher ensured that all parts of the tool were completely answered, thereby assuring the comprehensiveness of the data collection.

Afterward, the researcher tallied all the results and submitted them to a statistician for data treatment. After getting the data from the statistician, the researcher asked again for permission to interview the selected participants. Like the process for quantitative data gathering, for the qualitative phase, the researcher also explains the ethical considerations, the objectives, the process, and the proposed output of the study. The researcher could record and transcribe the answers of the chosen participants. The qualitative results were used to strengthen the researcher's quantitative data results.

Data Analysis

To interpret the different data gathered, the following statistical techniques and procedures were

Frequency Count. This was used to determine the number of responses for each item and to find the number of respondents for each item and to find the number of respondents for each category of variables. This statistical tool was used in summarizing the different data gathered using survey questionnaires and was expressed it into frequency distribution.

Percentage. This statistics was utilized to determine the relationship of the frequency of responses over the total responses.

Ranking. This was used to arrange data in a series of ascending or descending order of importance. In this study, the item with the highest frequency or weighted mean got the highest rank and the lowest also got the lowest rank.

Weighted Mean. This method was employed to interpret the organizational and policy practices as perceived by the respondents.

T-test. This statistical tool was a tool used in determining if the perceptions of the respondents regarding a certain variables differ from each other or not. To interpret the F – value, the researcher set the level of significance at 0.05 and 0.01 with the assigned degrees of freedoms.

The conditions set in decision making were as follows:

Accept H_0 if the F – value is less than the tabular at 0.05 level of significance.

Reject H_0 if the F – value is greater than the tabular t at 0.05 level of significance.

If the F –value exceeds tabular at 0.05: hence significant; if F – value exceeds tabular t at 0.01; hence highly significant.

Pearson’s r . This statistics was used in validating the research instrument in association with the Test- Retest Method.

Correlation Coefficient. This was employed to determine or measure the degree of relationship between the two variables.

On the other hand, to interpret the qualitative result, the researcher identifies recurring themes or patterns in the data. This was done by looking for commonalities, differences, or trends that emerge across the dataset. Afterwards, the researchers organized the findings into themes or categories.

Moreover, it involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within the data. Themes represent significant findings related to the research questions.

Steps are familiarization, coding, theme development, reviewing themes, and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher believed that ethical considerations in research are paramount to ensuring the dignity, rights, safety, and well-being of participants involved in any study. Thus, applying it to research must be a priority.

Participants of both quantitative and qualitative participants were fully informed about the nature of the research, its purpose, potential risks, benefits, and their rights before they agree to participate. Informed consent were voluntary and obtained without coercion.

Moreover, researcher ensures that participants' personal information remains confidential and that their privacy is protected throughout the study. Data were anonymized to prevent identification of individuals.

The researcher strives to minimize any potential physical, psychological, social, or economic harm that participants might experience as a result of their involvement in the research. This includes careful consideration of risks and benefits.

And lastly, Conflict of Interest were avoided. Researcher disclose any potential conflicts of interest that could influence the conduct or outcomes of the research, and take steps to minimize or manage these conflicts appropriately.

To summarize, the researcher conducted the research with honesty, integrity, and transparency, and report the findings accurately and objectively.

Results and Discussion

This section of the study gives the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents. Such presentation is in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Level of Organizational Management Practices of the Non-Government Organization

In Terms of Planning

Table 1. *Level of Organizational Management Practices of the Non-Government Organization in Terms of Planning*

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>The organization...</i>				
1.	creates and maintain a shared Vision and Goals for organization development and learning through community consultation.	4.67	Always	1
2.	develops policies and procedures which are consistent with the vision and mission.	4.57	Always	3
3.	Commits to a process of development that responds to and manages the processes that lead to sustained improvement.	4.50	Always	4
4.	Implements, monitors, and evaluates the organization's improvement plan.	4.40	Always	5
5.	Maximizes the use of existing data in decision-making.	4.60	Always	2
6.	Ensures consistency of practice in critical Policy areas such as assessment and management.	4.50	Always	6
7.	Develops and implements a decision making policy which includes role statement for individual groups and explicit lines of authority.	4.33	Always	7
Composite Mean		4.51	Always	

As seen in Table 1, the respondents assessed that the organization always creates and maintains a shared Vision and Goals for organization development and learning through community consultation which got the highest weighted mean of 4.67 and the highest rank of 1. The findings suggest that the organization excels in creating and maintaining a shared vision and goals for organizational development and learning through community consultation.

Moreover, this result revealed that the organization is effective in engaging both internal and external stakeholders to develop a clear vision and goals, which serves as a solid foundation for its ongoing development and learning initiatives. This level of clarity and

engagement can lead to enhanced performance, innovation, and adaptability in a rapidly changing environment.

This is strongly supported by the following answers from the interview gathered by the researcher:

“bago kami gumawa and mag implement ng programs for the whole year, we make sure that it is aligned with our vision and mission”
P1

“dyan naka-base yung quality ng services naming sa beneficiaries, yung mission and vision namin”-P3

“Yes. Part of the program talaga is sharing to our beneficiaries our goals. In that way, mas madali on our part na i-explain, why we are extending our efforts to help them, because we are guided by our vision and goals.”-p5

This therefore strengthens the importance of vision, mission and goals in the planning process of the non government organizations.

This findings supports the study of Collins and Porras, (2008), while the vision explains the situation and the value of the organisation in the future, the mission provides us with the reasons for the existence of an organisation, which is not only in the competitive struggle for greater profits, but also in accepting the role of social responsibility and development of the social innovation (Roblek et al., 2018; Schimmenti et al., 2014).

Moreover, relative to the analysis of the study, the internal organisational environment includes the owners of the organisation, their proxies, managers and employees (Lipičnik, 2005). The importance of internal organisational representatives is to either formulate or decide on a mission based on mission, and it is possible both. Often is going for the executive management, because exactly the owners invest their assets in the organisation in order to enrich it (Duh, 2015).

The external stakeholders of the organisation are customers, suppliers, financiers, competitors, the public, holders of social infrastructure and public finances and other state institutions.

For external participants it is characteristic that they are not the designers of the mission and do not directly influence and do not decide on the design and implementation of organisation policies. They influence the policy of the organisation indirectly or are adapting to it (Duh, 2015).

In addition, the said group of respondents also affirmed that the organization always develops and implements a decision making policy which includes role statement for individual groups and explicit lines of authority which made the least weighted mean of 4.33 and the least rank of 7.

To validate the least in rank, the following statements were emphasized by the chosen participants of the study.

“we cannot base our policies sa policy ng iba. But, we do benchmarks para makatulong sa planning”-p1

“May consultant kame.”-p4

“kailangan i-follow syempre yung decision, hindi lang ng sakin, but also the majority”-p5

The findings revealed that the respondents generally agreed that the organization consistently develops and enforces a decision-making policy. This policy likely outlines the roles and responsibilities of various groups within the organization and establishes clear lines of authority, ensuring that decision-making processes are structured and efficient.

However, the fact that this aspect received the least rank suggests that it was considered one of the most positively perceived aspects among all the criteria or items being assessed, yet needs to have improvement in this area.

The composite mean of 4.51 signified that the Non-Government Organizations level of management in terms of planning was always practiced. This also signifies that planning is deeply ingrained within the management culture of NGOs, playing a vital role in their ability to navigate challenges, seize opportunities, and achieve their mission-driven goals.

This finding also supports the qualitative part answered by the participants through interviews.

“may planning kame. Systematized”-p3

“in the planning, involved din yung major partners namin”-p4

The plan essentially focuses on the future and suggests measures that an organization must take to achieve its goals. It also helps in establishing concurrence around the desired results of the destined objectives. It directs an organization towards its goals as well as reviews and adjusts the overall direction of the organization in response to changing circumstances. Furthermore, it filters the problems that prevent organizational growth and progress and suggests suitable measures and steps in correcting these issues.

An effective planning is a result of disciplined efforts which ultimately define an organization, shapes and guides its activities and functions, classifies its services and the reasons behind its functions and services along with a strong focus on the future. It communicates the overall journey of an organization, the necessary actions that are needed to be taken for its growth and development and also the ways by which it will assess its progress and evaluate its achievements. (Khuski, 2022)

Table 2. *Level of Organizational Management Practices of the Non-Government Organization in Terms of Organizing*

Indicators		Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>The organization...</i>				
1.	Promotes environment where everyone is relaxed, friendly and ease during meetings and other discussions.	4.23	Always	2
2.	Encourages decision-making throughout the organization and operate among themselves and with their subordinates as a group.	3.97	Often	5
3.	Organizes personnel to participate in the planning of programs.	4.33	Always	1
4.	Has adequate staff with specific roles to perform.	4.17	Often	3
5.	Is updated on the processes of organizing the transactions, activities and programs.	4.03	Often	4
Composite Mean		4.15	Often	

As given in Table 2, the respondents agreed that the organization always organizes personnel to participate in the planning of programs which made the highest weighted mean of 4.33 and the highest rank of 1. This indicates that involving personnel in program planning is highly valued and perceived as a significant strength of the organization according to the respondents. This practice likely contributes positively to employee engagement, ownership of projects, and overall effectiveness of program planning and implementation within the organization.

This further explains in the responses of the participants during the interview, that personnel were involved in organizing events and programs.

“lahat ng staff involved. Hindi pwedeng kame lang na nasa higher.”-p

“since, konti lang yung staff ko, it is easy on our part to involve everyone, and our partners sa organization ng programs”-p5

“we consider them as our consultant also, the personnel. Their ideas are welcome”-p2

This is supported by the study of Posey, (n.d), who says that high involvement in the process by a variety of stakeholders tends to generate better outcomes and a greater sense of ownership. Many organizations are using broad engagement strategies to increase participation in and commitment to strategic planning.

This also agreed by Graham (2023), by involving employees in the planning process, businesses can ensure that their values and priorities are aligned, and that everyone is working towards a common goal. In addition to prioritizing people, purpose is a crucial ingredient for planning a happy and successful year.

However, the said group of respondents also answered that the organization often encourages decision-making throughout the organization and operate among themselves and with their subordinates as a group which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.97 and the least rank of 7. This safely concludes that the finding that the organization often encourages decision-making throughout the organization but still yielded a relatively low weighted mean and rank can be explained by the prevailing organizational culture that plays a crucial role in shaping employees' perceptions of decision-making.

The following statement below revealed that they encourage decision-making, hence, other factors, such as external stakeholders and partners should also be given opportunity to be involved.

“Maybe because, we cannot fully reply on the decision on the majority because we have partners din. We also balance what they want and what they do not want. But it doesn't mean na may conflict”-p3

“I do not think so. Kase involved naman lahat dapat”-p 5

“Kaya siguro sya least, because we have external people din to decide”-p1

The composite mean of 4.15 concluded that the Non-Government Organizations level of management in terms of organizing was often practiced.

This means that overall, in terms of organizing reflects positively on the management practices of NGOs, highlighting their ability to operate efficiently, adapt to change, foster collaboration, and achieves meaningful impact in their respective fields.

Research on organizing programs in non-government organizations (NGOs) reveals the significant influence of donors on governance practices (Lacruz, 2019). This is particularly evident in the temporary governance structures of sponsored projects, which are shaped by donor pressure and compliance requirements. The use of project-based organization is also highlighted as a key strategy for local development in NGOs, with a focus on the contextual and historical factors that drive this approach (Navarro-Flores, 2011). The role of voluntary programs in incentivizing socially beneficial actions beyond legal requirements is explored, with a particular emphasis on the design and effectiveness of these programs (Potoski, 2009). Lastly, the challenges faced by NGOs in conducting public relations activities, particularly in the context of limited economic resources, are discussed (Bronstein, 2006).

Table 3. *Level of Organizational Management Practices of the Non-Government Organization in Terms of Staffing*

Indicators		Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
<i>The organization...</i>				
1.	Determines the professional development needs and goals of its personnel.	4.50	Always	2
2.	Motivates personnel to increase their work performance.	4.57	Always	1
3.	Has auxiliary services that support the overall organization management.	4.43	Always	3
4.	Provide adequate resources to staff for proper execution of NGO activities and programs.	4.27	Always	4
5.	Has consistent coordination with its staff in decision-making.	4.13	Often	5
Composite Mean		4.38	Always	

As written in Table 3, the respondents answered that the organization always motivates personnel to increase their work performance which obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.57 and the highest rank of 1. This means that the organization consistently motivates its personnel to enhance their work performance, and this aspect was rated very highly and considered the most important among the factors examined.

It is relative with the responses of the participants during the interview. Their means if motivating their personnel is through attending seminars and work-life balance.

"They enjoy their rights as employees. Leaves, incentives, perfect attendance incentives"-p1

"I always encourage them to attend seminar."-p2

"Trainings and seminars, and ma-feel nila na involved sila"-p3

In order to ensure competitive ability, the quality of human resources, their management, and related measurement and performance assessment are at the forefront of company interest. Employee assessment affects the performance, development and motivation of people and also provides the necessary information about the employees. It allows the organization to monitor employee performance and compare their work with other collaborators. Szabo, et.al. (2017).

Moreover, a range of strategies can be employed to motivate personnel and increase their work performance (Stroh, 2001). Non-financial motivation, such as recognition and appreciation, can be particularly effective in this regard (Achim, 2013). It is important to understand employees' motivation needs and group them accordingly (Hitka, 2009). Factors such as higher salaries, extra bonuses, and better workplace conditions can also significantly influence motivation and performance (Uka, 2021).

Meanwhile, the said group of respondents replied that the organization often has consistent coordination with its staff in decision-making which got the least weighted mean of 4.13 and the least rank of 5. This means that according to the group of respondents, the organization's coordination with its staff in decision-making is perceived to be less consistent compared to other aspects evaluated. This suggests a potential area for improvement in terms of involving employees in the decision-making process or ensuring consistency in how this coordination occurs.

The following statement below revealed that they encourage coordination and decision-making, hence, other factors, such as external stakeholders and partners should also be given opportunity to be involved.

"Sabi ko nga kanina, we cannot fully rely on the decision (staff) because we have partners din. We also balance what they want and what they do not want. But it doesn't mean na may conflict or di sila heard"-p3

"I do not think so. Kase involved naman lahat dapat"-p 5

"Yung answer ko kanina, kaya siguro sya least, because we have external people din to decide"-p1

To support this study, a range of studies have highlighted the importance of involving employees in decision-making processes. Singh (2023) and Adjei (2012) both emphasize the role of worker participation in empowering employees and reducing unrest. Decision-making in organizations has been the reserve of top management without the involvement of those on the lower ranks of the management ladder, yet they are the very people expected to carry the implementation of these decisions made by top management.

Moreover, Kok (2014) and J. (2021) further underscore the positive impact of employee involvement on organizational productivity, with J. (2021) specifically noting its role in enhancing commitment, creativity, and innovation. These findings collectively suggest that involving employees in decision-making can lead to a more engaged and productive workforce.

On the other hand, the composite mean of 4.38 inferred that the Non-Government Organizations level of management in terms of staffing was always practiced.

The findings suggest that according to the assessment, NGOs are perceived to excel in their staffing practices at the management level, with a high level of consistency in implementing these practices.

An effective Performance Management strategy can ensure that employees' activities and output are in line with the wider business objectives and can be critical to business success and employee productivity. Once in the job, it means a never-ending cycle of education, coaching and feedback. Turning every interaction between manager and employee into a learning experience and a chance for the employee to be heard. (NaturalHR, 2022)

Level of Program Practices of the Non-Government Organizations

In Terms of Program Outcomes (Effectiveness)

Table 4. Level of Program Practices of the Non-Government Organizations in Terms of Program Outcomes (Effectiveness)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The organization's programs are effectively achieved in contributing to the development of targeted beneficiaries.	4.27	Strongly Agree	2
2. The organization's programs are effective in addressing crosscutting issues	4.20	Agree	3
3. The organization's programs are effective in achieving beneficiaries satisfaction.	4.33	Strongly Agree	1
4. The organization's programs are effective in contributing to volunteers development	4.17	Agree	4
5. The organization commits to quality systems and standards in programs delivery.	4.07	Agree	5
6. The organization provides innovative services and projects.	4.00	Agree	8
7. The organization's stakeholders are satisfied due to the organization's programs.	4.03	Agree	6.5
8. The organizations has strong relationships with the community	4.03	Agree	6.5
Composite Mean	4.14	Agree	

As reflected in Table 4, the respondents strongly agreed that the the organization's programs are effective in achieving beneficiaries satisfaction which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.33 and the highest rank of 1. The researcher safely analyzes that the results underscores that the organization's programs are perceived as highly effective in satisfying the beneficiaries, as evidenced by the strong agreement among respondents, as well as the high ratings and ranking accorded to this aspect in the survey or study.

Moreover, the answer of the participants during the interview highlights the satisfaction of their beneficiaries in every program that they implements.

"We practice feed backing. Okay naman and we meet their expectations"-p1

"Sometimes, others will just get and leave, but majority will look back at you and say their gratitude"-p2

"I believe our programs are effective. Based sa evaluation. Syempre minsan we do evaluations, lalo na sa mga barangay officials. We asked them to evaluate our programs"-p4

This is supported by the study of Balaraju (2019) and Kala (2013) both found a significant correlation between NGO effectiveness and the quality of life and empowerment of beneficiaries, respectively.

Wellens (2016) noted that while most NPOs have mechanisms for beneficiary involvement, the impact on decision-making and output is weak but positive. Khan (2014) highlighted the role of NGO programs in the educational development of beneficiaries, with informal education and certain training dimensions significantly contributing to this development. These findings collectively underscore the positive impact of NGO programs on the well-being and development of their beneficiaries.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents only agreed that the organization provides innovative services and projects which computed the least weighted mean of 4.00 and the least rank of 8. In summary, while the respondents generally agreed that the organization provides innovative services and projects, their agreement was not as strong as in other areas assessed. The lower weighted mean and rank indicate that this aspect may not be perceived as highly significant or outstanding compared to others evaluated in the survey or study.

"we base our projects sa funding and budget, kaya the line up projects were the same palagi"-p2

"May specific projects lang kame. Depend sa NGO kung anong projects sila center, kame more on support sa poor community. Innovative projects maybe kapag ok na yung community na nagse-serve kame"-p3

"Crime watch kame. So we based our services and projects sa ganung aspect"-p4

NGOs face a range of challenges in implementing innovative services and projects. Semeno (2014) highlights the need for innovative social project design to meet the complex needs of the population. Božić (2022) further emphasizes the role of nonstate service providers, such as NGOs, in driving social innovation, particularly in challenging contexts.

However, Miković (2020) points out that these organizations often struggle with the integration of social capital and knowledge management, which are crucial for project success. Aruna (2015) adds that NGOs also grapple with internal and external management issues, including strategic planning, budgeting, and relationships with other stakeholders. These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of the problems faced by NGOs in implementing innovative services and projects.

The composite mean of 4.14 assumed that the respondents agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of program outcomes (effectiveness). This suggests a perceived alignment between the practices implemented by NGOs and the effectiveness of their programs in achieving desired outcomes.

The study of Balaraju, K(2019) revealed that Organizational effectiveness influences the NGOs performance in various important aspects like stakeholders' satisfaction, expertise solutions in their area of operation, goal achievement and innovation. NGOs operate in order to improve their beneficiaries' quality of life aspects. Whereas, measuring overall organizational effectiveness is an important issue which has been insufficiently researched. Determining whether an organization has been able to align their organizational processes with the programmatic impacts is necessary to assess their degree of success. Evaluating impacts and identifying indicators of organizational success are necessary to report to the public, funders and to improve the organization's level of effectiveness. Moreover, assessing the effectiveness of NGOs will help to focus more effectively on planned outcomes. Such outcomes might improve the socio-economic status of the beneficiaries and eventually provide quality of life experiences. Understanding the effectiveness of NGOs contributes to the development of their operational area and also to the beneficiaries.

In Terms of Program's Non-Financial Efficiency

Table 5. Level of Program Practices of the Non-Government Organizations in Terms of Program's Non-Financial Efficiency

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The organization uses proper activities to transform non-financial resources of the programs into outputs.	4.13	Agree	3
2. The organization recruits staff with the right skills, experience to achieve the planned outputs of programs.	4.27	Strongly Agree	2
3. The organization commits to time schedule to achieve the programs outputs.	4.30	Strongly Agree	1
4. The organization's programs provides a number of products/services as planned.	4.03	Agree	4
Composite Mean	4.18	Agree	

As revealed in Table 5 the respondents strongly agreed that the the organization commits to time schedule to achieve the programs outputs which reported the highest weighted mean of 4.30 and the highest rank of 1.

The findings underscores that respondents strongly agreed with the organization's commitment to adhering to time schedules to achieve program outputs. This high level of agreement was reflected in both the strong consensus among respondents and the high ratings and ranking accorded to this aspect.

Moreover, this findings support the answer of the participants on their interview on how committed they are on their time management.

"Since kasama sa annual plan, hindi pwedeng hindi natin susundin"-p1

"Once decided na naming, with our partners, strict na kames a schedule"-p2

"Our projects palagi involves stakeholders, si hindi pwedeng hindi susunod sa scheduled activities"-p5

Moreover, the said group of respondents only agreed that the organization's programs provides a number of products/services as planned which gave the least weighted mean of 4.03 and the least rank of 4. The researcher analyzes that the result indicates that while respondents generally agreed that the organization's programs provide products or services as planned, their agreement was not as strong as in other areas assessed. The lower weighted mean and rank suggest that this aspect may not be perceived as highly significant or outstanding compared to other factors evaluated in the survey or study.

"Every NGO may certain plans and projects according sa mission and goals namin"-p2

"Crime watch NGO namin. Dun lang yung programs na pino-provide namin"-p4

"Kami naman kalimitan projects ay ang beneficiaries are the poor sa community, so yun yung mission and goals namin"-p3

These findings were supported by the study of Mustaghis-ur-Rahman, (2007), that NGO services and projects are deeply rooted in their mission, which guides their operations and management. This mission-driven approach is particularly important for NGOs in developing countries, where it can strengthen their strategy and commitment to local development (Navarro-Flores, 2011).

It is therefore agreed by Kimani (2022) that the influence of mission and vision on the financial sustainability of NGOs has been highlighted, with a strong mission and vision being linked to organizational success.

The composite mean of 4.18 implied that the respondents agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of program's non-financial efficiency.

This finding indicates that respondents generally agreed with the level of program practices of NGOs concerning non-financial efficiency. This suggests that there is perceived alignment between the practices implemented by NGOs and their effectiveness in achieving program objectives beyond financial considerations.

Moreover, a range of studies have explored the program practices of NGOs in terms of non-financial efficiency. Kim (2018) and Özbek (2015) both used data envelopment analysis (DEA) to evaluate the efficiency of programs and fundraising activities in Korean and Turkish NPOs respectively. Kim found that 15 out of 22 NPOs were efficient in program efficiency, while Özbek identified the Turkish Diyanet Foundation as the most efficient NGO. Ecer (2017) highlighted the relationship between revenue composition and economic-financial efficiency, with a focus on the role of commercial revenues and donations.

In Terms of Programs Impact

Table 6. Level of Program Practices of the Non-Government Organizations in Terms of Programs Impact

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The organization's programs contribute to achieving the overall objective of your organization.	4.60	Strongly Agree	2
2. The organization's programs are effective in causing direct effects on the community.	4.73	Strongly Agree	1
3. The organization's programs are effective in causing indirect effects on the community.	4.50	Strongly Agree	3
4. The organization's programs are effective in creating a long term effect or at social, economic, technological level as resulted from the programs.	4.43	Strongly Agree	4
Composite Mean	4.57	Strongly Agree	

As discussed in Table, the respondents strongly agreed that the organization's programs are effective in causing direct effects on the community which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.73 and the highest rank of 1. The result highlights that the surveyed individuals strongly believe that the organization's programs are highly successful in directly impacting the community, as evidenced by their high rating and ranking in the evaluation.

This strongly emphasized on the answers of the selected participants during the interview.

"Kanina nga I mentioned na nag-practice kame feed backing. Okay naman and we meet their expectations"-p1

"Sa answer ko kanina. Sometimes, others will just get and leave, but majority will look back at you and say their thank you to us"-p2

"Ganun din sa sagot ko kanina. (I believe our programs are effective. Based sa evaluation. Syempre minsan we do evaluations, lalo na sa mga barangay officials. We asked them to evaluate our programs)"-p4

Balaraju (2019) and Kala (2013) both found a significant correlation between NGO effectiveness and the quality of life and empowerment of beneficiaries, respectively. Wellens (2016) noted that while most NPOs have mechanisms for beneficiary involvement, the impact on decision-making and output is weak but positive.

On the other hand, Khan (2014) highlighted the role of NGO programs in the educational development of beneficiaries, with informal education and certain training dimensions significantly contributing to this development. These findings collectively underscore the positive impact of NGO programs on the well-being and development of their beneficiaries.

Additionally, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that the organization's programs are effective in creating a long term effect or at social, economic, technological level as resulted from the programs which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.43 and the least rank of 4.

The finding implies that while respondents still acknowledged the effectiveness of the organization's programs in creating long-term effects at social, economic, and technological levels, they did so to a slightly lesser extent compared to the direct effects on the community.

The result of the interviews revealed that, to have a long term effects, projects should be sustainable and should be innovative. This reveals with the statement answered by the participants below:

"Siguro kaya least, kase we cannot sustain the programs"-p1

"I think we need na katulad nang kanina, innovative programs"-p2

"Innovation siguro para sustained na din ang programs -p3

NGOs do not always result in positive impacts. There are some criticisms towards the impacts of NGOs. NGOs should scale up its

successful strategies by collaborating with other organizations and government, while the government should give some support to NGOs in order to better meet the people's needs in their life. (Xi & Hossain, 2016)

Moreover, recent studies have highlighted the importance of sustainable and innovative projects in the NGO sector. Dyck (2019) emphasizes the need for non-centrist approaches to facilitate the adoption of sustainable innovations in low-income countries, while Daneshpour (2020) suggests the use of open innovation to integrate sustainability into project portfolio management. These studies underscore the potential of innovative strategies in promoting sustainability and enhancing the effectiveness of NGO projects.

The composite mean of 4.57 reported that the respondents strongly agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of program impact.

The finding suggests that the respondents held a positive perception of NGO program practices, strongly agreeing that these practices effectively result in meaningful program impacts. This high level of agreement, reflected indicates a consensus among respondents regarding the efficacy of NGO programs in achieving their intended goals and making a positive difference in the communities they serve.

Recent studies have highlighted the positive impact of NGOs in the Philippines. Atienza (2021) emphasizes the importance of local NGOs in post-disaster settings, particularly in housing and livelihood projects. Hirai (2021) identifies key factors in NGO interventions that help at-risk youths escape the poverty trap, including mentorship, comprehensive interventions, and transitional work opportunities. These findings underscore the crucial role of NGOs in addressing social and economic challenges in the country.

In Terms of Partnership

Table 7. Level of Program Practices of the Non-Government Organizations in Terms of Partnership

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
The organization considers collaborative partnership in its operations.	4.00	Agree	2
The organization attracts local partners for the organization's programs.	4.07	Agree	1
The organization attracts international partners for the organization's programs.	3.93	Agree	3
The organization attracts private sector partners for the organization's programs.	3.60	Agree	4
Composite Mean	3.90	Agree	

As seen in Table 7, the respondents agreed that the organization attracts local partners for the organization's programs which made the highest weighted mean of 4.07 and the highest rank of 1.

The above finding highlights that respondents agreed that the organization effectively collaborates with local partners for its programs. This collaboration likely contributes to the organization's ability to leverage local expertise, resources, and networks, ultimately enhancing the impact and sustainability of its programs within the community.

This is relevant to the answer of the participants during the interview, on how they involve local government unit and community leaders as some of their partners.

"Tap lagi naming ofcourse ang LGU Dasma, para mas easy magbigay ng information"-p1

"LGU and community leaders, palaging partner namin"-p2

"Even NGO kame, we should inform and involve the local officials"-p5

Moreover, Pozil (2017) emphasized the role of trust in informal partnerships between NGOs and local governments. Informal partnerships between nonprofit organizations (NPOs) and local governments represent a winning combination for affective positive social change in communities. These partnerships thrive on the development and sustainment of trust as a guiding force between NPO executives and their local government counterparts.

Moreover, the said group of respondents also agreed that the organization attracts private sector partners for the organization's programs which made the least weighted mean of 3.60 and the least rank of 4.

This finding suggests that while respondents still recognized the organization's ability to attract private sector partners, they did so to a lesser extent compared to its partnerships with local entities. This suggests that there may be areas for improvement or opportunities for the organization to strengthen its engagement with the private sector in support of its programs.

Moreover, the statements below were the responses of the participants on their partnerships to private entities. Majority agreed that they needed improvement to strengthen its engagement with the private sector.

"Meron kameng private partners, pero hindi madaling makipag partner, since madami na din NGO dito sa Dasma"-p1

"Kulang kames a private partners, siguro that's the next agenda naming, yung mag increase partnership namin"-p2

"yung naabutan kong partners naming na private sector, yun pa din until today. Siguro we need expand na din the quantity of our partners. Hindi naman mahirap makipag partner sa kanila"-p5

Recent studies have highlighted a range of challenges and opportunities in the partnership between the private sector and NGOs. Hakkarainen (2020) and Haque (2020) both underscore the complexities and potential pitfalls of such collaborations, with Hakkarainen focusing on the internal challenges faced by NGOs and Haque critiquing the role of NGOs as partners in governance. On the other hand, Franzén (2019) and Indira (2023) offer a more optimistic view, emphasizing the potential for cross-sector partnerships to drive positive change.

The composite mean of 3.90 inferred that the respondents agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of partnership.

This finding suggests that respondents generally agreed with the level of program practices related to partnership exhibited by NGOs. However, the composite mean score of 3.90 indicates that while there is agreement, it may not be as strong or unanimous as in some other areas. This could imply that there may be room for improvement in how NGOs engage in partnerships, potentially through enhancing collaboration strategies, communication channels, or resource-sharing mechanisms.

Kamande (2014) identified various factors that influence partnerships between NGOs and private sector organizations, and Finnell (2012) explored the potential of e-government to simplify the partnership process between NGOs and government agencies. These studies collectively underscore the potential for partnerships to enhance the effectiveness and reach of NGOs, but also highlight the importance of trust, factors influencing partnerships, and the potential of digital tools in this context.

Moreover, organizational engagement and partnership consist of collaborative relationships within the agency and with external partners, families, youth, and community and cultural groups to support service integration and inform improved practices. Research on the impact of partnerships between non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and other entities has highlighted several key factors. Kimani (2014) found that partnerships can positively influence the performance of local NGOs.

Additionally, Indira (2023) reveals that NGOs are engaging with companies mainly for accessing financial resources. Since the companies are having control over finances, companies lead the partnerships. There is good communication between NGOs and their business partners. Transformative changes are observed in some NGOs by improving their capabilities. Suggestions are made based on the study to realize maximum collaborative social value from the engagements.

Relationship Between the Levels of Organizational Management and Program Practices of Non-Government Organizations

Table 8. *Relationship Between the Levels of Organizational Management and Program Practices of Non-Government Organizations*

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of Organizational Management Practices in Terms of Planning Versus Level of Program Practices:				
Program Outcomes	0.39	0.03312	Reject Ho	Significant
Programs Non-Financial Efficiency	0.54	0.00207	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Programs Impact	0.49	0.00598	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Partnership	0.37	0.04416	Reject Ho	Significant
Level of Organizational Management Practices in Terms of Organizing Versus Level of Program Practices:				
Program Outcomes	0.50	0.00490	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Programs Non-Financial Efficiency	0.48	0.00727	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Programs Impact	0.22	0.24274	Failed to Reject Ho	Significant
Partnership	0.37	0.04416	Reject Ho	Significant
Level of Organizational Management Practices in Terms of Staffing Versus Level of Program Practices:				
Program Outcomes	0.38	0.03833	Reject Ho	Significant
Programs Non-Financial Efficiency	0.39	0.03312	Reject Ho	Significant
Programs Impact	0.47	0.00877	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Partnership	0.21	0.26536	Failed to Reject Ho	Significant

As stated in Table 8, when the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of planning were compared to their responses on the level of program practices, the computed r-values of 0.54 for program’s non-financial efficiency and 0.49 for program’s impact have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

In addition, the computed r-values of 0.39 for program outcomes and 0.37 for partnership have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely inferred that the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of planning have high significant relationships to their responses on the level of program practices such as program’s non-financial efficiency and program’s impact; and significant relationships in terms of program outcomes and partnership.

This indicates that the way respondents perceive an organization's planning practices has a notable impact on their perceptions of various aspects of the organization's program implementation, including efficiency, impact, outcomes, and partnerships. This underscores the importance of effective organizational management and planning in driving successful program implementation and achieving desired outcomes.

Effective organizational management and planning are crucial for successful program implementation and desired outcomes (Kabeyi, 2019; Kifordu, 2020; Pandey, 2021; Kabrilyants, 2021). These processes involve self-assessment, reorganization, and a holistic approach to strategy formulation and implementation (Kabeyi, 2019). They also require a focus on improving productivity, attaining organizational goals, and meeting customer needs (Kifordu, 2020). Strategic planning, in particular, is highlighted as a key factor in achieving sustained organizational success (Pandey, 2021).

Moreover, when the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of organizing were compared to their responses on the level of program practices, the computed r-values of 0.50 for program's outcomes, and 0.48 for program's non-financial efficiency have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

Additionally, the computed r-values of 0.22 for program's impact, and 0.37 for partnership have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely deduced that the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of organizing have high significant relationships to their responses on the level of program practices such as program's outcomes and program's non-financial efficiency; and significant relationships on program's impact and partnership. These safely deduced that the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of organizing have high significant relationships to their responses on the level of program practices such as program's outcomes and program's non-financial efficiency; and significant relationships on program's impact and partnership.

Lastly, when the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of staffing were compared to their responses on the level of program practices, the computed r-value of 0.47 for program's impact has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

Moreover, the computed r-values of 0.38 for program's outcomes, 0.39 for program's non-financial efficiency, and 0.21 for partnership have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely implied that the responses of the respondents on the level of organizational management practices in terms of staffing have high significant relationships to their responses on the level of program practices such as program's impact; and no significant relationships in terms of program's outcomes, program's non-financial efficiency and partnership. While respondents perceive a significant relationship between organizational staffing practices and program impact, they do not perceive similar relationships with program outcomes, non-financial efficiency, and partnership. This highlights the complexity of factors influencing program effectiveness and the need for comprehensive assessment and improvement strategies beyond staffing alone.

This findings support the study by Lievens (2020) emphasizes the importance of personnel selection, showing its positive impact on both individual and organizational performance.

Norze (2020) further highlights the influence of staff expertise on program quality in youth development, suggesting that staff training in key areas can significantly enhance program effectiveness. Howells (2020) underscores the need for effective staffing, recruitment, and HR management, emphasizing the benefits of a robust staff training program and the importance of consistent messaging and feedback.

Conclusions

The result of the analysis and interpretation of the different data gave the following conclusions.

The Non-Government Organizations level of management in terms of planning was always practiced, thus, this also signifies that planning is deeply ingrained within the management culture of NGOs.

Non-Government Organizations often practice organizing. This means that overall, in terms of organizing reflects positively on the management practices of NGOs, highlighting their ability to operate efficiently, adapt to change, foster collaboration, and achieves meaningful impact in their respective fields.

On the other hand, Non-Government Organizations level of management in terms of staffing was always practiced. This concludes that NGOs are perceived to excel in their staffing practices at the management level, with a high level of consistency in implementing these practices.

Alignment between the practices implemented by NGOs and the effectiveness of their programs in achieving desired outcomes is agreed by the respondents.

Respondents generally agreed with the level of program practices of NGOs concerning non-financial efficiency.

Respondents strongly agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of program impact. The finding suggests that the respondents held a positive perception of NGO program practices, strongly agreeing that these practices effectively result in meaningful program impacts. This high level of agreement, reflected indicates a consensus among respondents regarding the efficacy of NGO programs in achieving their intended goals and making a positive difference in the communities they

serve.

Respondents agreed on the level of program practices of Non-Government Organizations in terms of partnership. This concludes that respondents generally agreed with the level of program practices related to partnership exhibited by NGOs. However, it indicates that while there is agreement, it may not be as strong or unanimous as in some other areas. This could imply that there may be room for improvement in how NGOs engage in partnerships, potentially through enhancing collaboration strategies, communication channels, or resource-sharing mechanisms.

Based on the different findings of the study, the following are the recommendations drawn.

Non-Government Organizations should adopt an integrated approach to management practices, ensuring alignment between planning, organizing, and staffing efforts. This can be achieved through cross-functional collaboration, clear communication channels, and cohesive decision-making processes.

To continuously assess and improve the operations of NGO, regular evaluation of organizational management practices and their impact on program outcomes should be done. This may involve collecting feedback from stakeholders, conducting performance reviews, and utilizing data-driven metrics to identify areas for improvement and make informed decisions.

NGOs should invest in capacity building initiatives to enhance the skills and capabilities of staff members involved in program implementation. This may include training programs, professional development opportunities, and knowledge sharing platforms to ensure that staff is equipped to effectively execute their roles.

NGOs should strengthen partnerships, particularly with the private sector. Recognizing the significant relationship between organizational management practices and partnership effectiveness, organizations should prioritize the development and nurturing of strategic partnerships. This involves building trust, fostering collaboration, and aligning goals and objectives to maximize collective impact.

To future researchers, while this study focused on specific aspects of organizational management practices of NGOs such as planning, organizing, and staffing, they could consider a broader range of organizational factors. This may include leadership styles, communication strategies, culture, and organizational structure, providing a more comprehensive understanding of their influence on program outcomes.

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